

where, a refers to concentration of Ph_3P and x to the concentration of Ph_3PO formed during the reaction. The rate constant values are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE REACTION

Time (h) min	215° k (mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)	225° k (mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)	235° k (mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)
0	0	0	0
10	42.4	8.3	4.9
20	28.3	4.7	0.46
30	21.0	7.4	2.4
40	11.9	5.9	4.0
50	—	5.1	5.3

$$a = 2.56 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol.}$$

The data in Table 1 are consistent with a second order rate kinetics. It may be seen from the Table that the values of k fall in magnitude on changing the temperature from 215 to 235°. It was observed that at a temperature higher than 235°, viz. 245°, there was greater inconsistency in the k values. Hence, it is inferred from this data that the transfer of oxygen takes place more efficiently in the vicinity of 215° for the reaction under consideration. The mechanism of oxygen transfer is proposed as

This study fairly demonstrates that ir spectroscopy is suitable for studying such atom transfer reactions.

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Debenzylation and Oxidative Cyclisation of Certain 2-S-Benzyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets with Elemental Sulphur

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THIOCARBAMIDE has been used as a debenzylating agent in the debenzylation of 2-S-benzyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (1) earlier¹. The present paper describes the debenzylation and oxidative cyclisation of certain 2-S-benzyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets using elemental sulphur.

2-S-Benzyl-1,5-diphenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (1a) on reaction with elemental sulphur in presence of pyridine in boiling ethanolic medium afforded two products, one with m.p. 178° and the other with m.p. 203°. The ir spectrum of the product with m.p. 178° showed the presence of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (1580), ν_{ringNH} (3350) and $\nu_{\text{S-S}}$ (500 cm^{-1}). The product was assigned the structure, 3,5-diphenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (2a) on the basis undepressed m.m.p. with the authentic sample². The product with m.p. 203° was found desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. Its ir spectrum showed the presence of ν_{NH} (3140) and $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$ (1060 cm^{-1}). On the basis of these observations, it has been detected as 1-phenyl-3-(benzothiazole-2-yl)thiocarbamide (4a). This has been further confirmed by its comparison with an authentic sample³.

Neither benzylmercaptan nor dibenzyldisulphide could be isolated in the reaction. However, an odour of benzaldehyde was quite perceptible.

This reaction has been found to be capable of extension to other 2-S-benzyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (1b and 1c) and the corresponding 1,2,4-dithiazolidines (2b and 2c) and 1-phenyl-3-(chlorobenzothiazol-2-yl)thiocarbamides (4b and 4c) have been isolated (Table 1).

TABLE 1—3,5-DIARYLIMINO-1,2,4-DITHIAZOLIDINES (2) AND 1-PHENYL-3-(BENZOTHAZOL-2-YL)THIOCARBAMIDES (4)

Compd. 1 (2 g)	Compd 2 (m.p.)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		Compd. 4 (m.p.)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
		N	S		N	S
1a	2a (178°)	14.69 (14.59)	22.86 (22.46)	4a (203°)	14.45 (14.59)	22.76 (22.46)
1b	2b (192°)	12.98 (13.14)	20.91 (20.03)	4b (235°)	13.41 (13.14)	20.48 (20.03)
1c	2c (194°)	13.40 (13.14)	20.55 (20.03)	4c (225°)	13.23 (13.14)	20.46 (20.03)

Mechanism: Sulphur in spite of its 16 lone electron pairs is a Lewis acid rather than a base and exists as cycloocta sulphur. It is quite probable, as suggested by Mayer⁴, that through the opening of the cycloocta sulphur ring with a base (pyridine), a dipolar open chain structure (6) an octasulphide may result. This octasulphide will bring about the debenzilation. The further possible stages of the reaction are indicated below :

(Found: N, 10.10; S, 14.78. C₂₁H₁₈N₂S₂Cl requires N, 10.21; S, 14.51%) have been prepared for the first time by the interaction of phenylisothiocyanate and *S*-benzyl-1-*p*-chlorophenylisothiocarbamide and *S*-benzyl-1-*m*-chlorophenylisothiocarbamide, respectively, by the extension of the above procedure.

Interaction of 2-S-benzyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (1) and elemental sulphur in presence

Experimental

The required 2-*S*-benzyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (1) have been prepared by the interaction of phenylisothiocyanate and *S*-benzyl-1-arylisothiocarbamide in dry benzene⁵. 2-*S*-Benzyl-1-*p*-chlorophenyl-5-phenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (1b), m.p. 120° (Found: N, 10.51; S, 14.88. C₂₁H₁₈N₂S₂Cl requires N, 10.21; S, 14.51%), and 2-*S*-benzyl-1-*m*-chlorophenyl-5-phenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (1c), m.p. 102°

of pyridine: Formation of 3,5-diarylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (2) and 1-aryl-3-(benzothiazol-2-yl)thiocarbamide (4): To an ethanolic suspension of 2-*S*-benzyl-1,5-diphenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (1a; 2 g in 20 ml) was added elemental sulphur (1 g) and pyridine (1 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h when hydrogen sulphide was eliminated. After 3 h, the elemental sulphur was filtered off and the filtrate diluted with excess of water when an oily mass was obtained. A distinct smell of benzaldehyde

was quite perceptible when the reaction mixture was acidified with aqueous HCl (6 N). The oily mass was washed thoroughly with water and then triturated several times with petroleum ether followed by ethanol, when a yellow solid was obtained. It was dried, washed with diethyl ether and crystallised from ethanol/glacial acetic acid, m.p. 178° (2a).

The ethereal washings on evaporation afforded a small amount of a pale yellow product, crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 203° (4a).

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Application of Chlorotrimethylsilane. Reaction of Bromonitroolefins with Chlorotrimethylsilane

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RECENT publications¹⁻³ have highlighted diverse utility of chlorotrimethylsilane (ClMe₃Si) as an important reagent for organic synthesis. This reagent can be used either directly or in combination with a suitable metal. The versatile nature of chlorotrimethylsilane in chemical transformations prompted us to carry out the reaction of 3β-acetoxy-7α-bromo-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1)⁴, 3β-chloro-7α-bromo-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (2)⁴ and 4β,7α-dibromo-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (3)⁴ with chlorotrimethylsilane in presence of zinc dust which gave 3β-acetoxy-5α-cholestan-6-one (4), 3β-chloro-5α-cholestan-6-one (5) and 5α-cholestan-6-one (6), respectively in excellent yield. Our study showed that chlorotrimethylsilane reduces the olefinic nitro group present in ring 'B' of steroids to ketone and debromination also takes place from C₇ and C₄ positions.

	X	R ₁	R ₂		X
1	OAc	H	Br	4	OAc
2	Cl	H	Br	5	Cl
3	H	Br	Br	6	H

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer. Nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Varian A60 instrument using TMS as an internal standard.

Reaction of chlorotrimethylsilane and zinc dust with steroidal compounds 1 to 3: A typical procedure is described for 1. To a solution of 3β-acetoxy-7α-bromo-6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1)⁴ (2 g) in ether (100 ml) was added chlorotrimethylsilane (10 ml). To this mixture, zinc dust (6 g) was added in small portions over a period of 30 min. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 4 h at room temperature (the progress of the reaction was checked through tlc). At the completion of the reaction, zinc dust was filtered and the solution was washed successively with water, sodium bicarbonate solution (2%) and water. Ether layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvent gave 3β-acetoxy-5α-cholestan-6-one (4) which was crystallised from alcohol (1.70 g), m.p. and m.m.p. 127° (lit.⁵ 127°).

Similar treatment of 2 (2 g) with zinc dust (6 g) and chlorotrimethylsilane (10 ml) gave 3β-chloro-5α-cholestan-6-one (5) (1.75 g), m.p. and m.m.p. 128° (lit.⁶ 129°).

The compound (3) (2 g) similarly provided the expected 5α-cholestan-6-one (6) (1.7 g), m.p. and m.m.p. 97° (lit.⁷ 98°).

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